

Prediction of ceramic matrix composites lifetime in high temperature static fatigue based on a probabilistic fracture mechanics model

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SUMMARY

The time-to-failure of ceramic matrix composites is controlled by fibre fractures, during static fatigue, in air, at temperatures ranging from 400°C to 1200°C. A probabilistic fracture mechanics model is proposed to predict variations in fiber tow flaw density functions. Strength-Probability-Time diagrams for composites are established.

Keywords: prediction, lifetime, flaw density function, subcritical crack growth, probabilistic fracture.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) are very attractive for structural applications at high temperatures. They are now considered for introduction in aircraft engines. Thus, the control and the prediction of CMC lifetime becomes a critical issue.

The structural performances of CMCs are controlled by fiber strengths. Multifilament tows represent a fundamental entity in textile composites. They progressively carry the load as the matrix is damaged, and they control the composite ultimate failure [1]. Multifilament tows are elastic and damage tolerant. Furthermore, under the application of stress less than that to induce short term failure, there is a regime where subcritical crack growth can lead to failure in finite times. SiC multifilament tows are sensitive to this phenomenon at temperatures ranging from 400°C to 1200°C [2, 3], in air.

This paper proposes a model of delayed failure for CMCs based on a probabilistic fracture mechanics-based approach.

APPROACH

The model is based on the distribution of fracture inducing flaws described using appropriate flaw density functions. Changes in the flaw density functions caused by environmental effects and applied load are introduced (figure 1). The kinetics control time to failure.

RESULTS

The parameters relative to the flaw density functions were derived from tensile tests and fatigue tests at high temperatures on SiC-based multifilament tows. Strength-Probability-Time diagrams for CMCs were calculated using the model. They are compared to experimental results. This approach allows statistical features of stress-rupture time relations to be accounted for.

Figure 1: flaw density functions change under fibre damage effects

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References

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